

CHALLENGES AND SOLUTIONS OF FORMATION OF INNOVATIVE ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: *The essence of the innovation process in this article is about a new product or service, market implementation and the formation of an innovative economy.*

Key words: *economics, economics, modern technologies, entrepreneurs, competitive products, technical staff.*

In our country, the majority of the population and middle-level scientific and technical staff do not understand what an "innovative economy" is, but in developed western and eastern countries, every scientific and technical staff does it. are very familiar with the economics taught in the lim institutions. Most of our highly educated professionals with little knowledge of science and technology understand that an innovative economy is one in which everyone is an innovator. But in educational institutions around the world, innovative economics is studied in a unique sense and as a specific discipline. The main difference between the innovative economy and other specialized secular sciences is that it teaches the international market for advanced technologies and how to operate effectively in this market. Technology and, at the same time, the right to own intellectual property are the basis of the investment process for all manufacturing enterprises. In other words, if an entrepreneur wants to produce clothing as an example, he should start his business by first studying the available modern technologies and choosing and buying the best of them. In our country, if an entrepreneur wants to produce clothes, he starts by buying ready-made equipment without comparative study of the world's advanced technologies with the involvement of scientists and technicians in this field. Because he is not well versed in the technology available, it often turns out that the equipment is old, obsolete, or spiritually obsolete. Therefore, now it can never compete with entrepreneurs in other countries and even if it can find or export its products abroad, because the technology is old, it cannot make a big profit and cannot compete, and its business will go bankrupt. possible. A knowledge-based innovation economy, on the other hand, has a completely different development logic when it comes to the intellectual property market. Now it is not a modern machine or

equipment perfected by someone, but a technological process created with deep thought by professionals in the field at a professional level. Only then will the experimental technology be sold to investors, who will begin the production process on a trial basis. If in this case the quality of the product produced as an experiment meets the requirements of the world, the machines will be purchased together with the technology. In our country, it is common to buy machines and equipment at risk and start production without thinking about the consequences and conducting scientific and technical research.

Modern industry, created as a result of the innovation process, is radically different from the industry of our time. Very large enterprises and industrial cities engaged in the same work are not necessary for a modern innovative economy. Innovative enterprises built on the basis of modern technologies, equipped with automatic equipment, computers and robots, can do the work of the entire population of the city and produce much more competitive products. Such modern technologies are compact, economical, operate almost without human intervention and can meet all environmental requirements.

There are a number of steps that can be taken to improve the technology transfer situation. For example, when concluding investment agreements with large foreign companies (transnational corporations), it is necessary to establish a joint or foreign research center (or department) in Uzbekistan, provided that they train local staff, and approve the results of scientific research in domestic enterprises. You can enter items that hold In order to ensure the economic development of the regions of the republic and increase the scientific and technical level of the population, it is possible to pursue a policy of tax exemption for 3-4 years for foreign companies that create jobs on the basis of new technologies in remote areas. 50% tax exemption for companies that have transferred patented technologies and made direct foreign investments with production "nai-hai", provided that they start production and start production would increase.

Giving tax benefits to the income from the activities of non-governmental and non-profit organizations engaged in the provision of technology transfer services on the basis of the relevant legal framework would also have a positive effect. In general, in the next few years, it would be expedient to use the scientific, technical and industrial potential of developed countries as much as possible to effectively develop the innovation process in the country's economy. This can also be done by purchasing licenses for high-performance new technologies and introducing them to production and marketing with the help of Uzbek scientists and engineers.

The promotion of innovation in the media increases the creative activity of the general public and creates new thinking and a new way of life that encourages creativity. Therefore, the widespread promotion of the socio-political significance of innovations should be one of the main issues of public information policy. Solving this problem will

arouse great interest and positive attitude of the members of the society towards the innovative development of the country. To do this, it is necessary to explain in detail the vital importance of innovation in television, radio, magazines, newspapers and electronic publications, as well as in various conferences to improve the quality of life and material well-being of the population. creating a positive business environment is crucial. This requires ease of doing business in the country and a transparent and competitive economy. In particular, in order to accelerate innovation in Uzbekistan, it would be expedient to make changes in export-import operations, taxation laws and procedures for dealing with foreign exchange.

The new laws in the field of innovation provide a clear and unambiguous legal framework for the legal management of the interaction of entities engaged in innovative activities, the creation, financing, promotion, implementation, transfer and distribution of intellectual property. must buy. One of the main issues in this regard is to address the issue of ownership of the results of intellectual activity created at the expense of the state budget.

Many do not understand such innovative technological changes, which are vital for the future of our country, and the allies can be only small and medium-sized business officials, educated government officials and qualified scientific and technical personnel. Therefore, with their help, all work should be started and the importance of innovative changes (if necessary, the innovative scientific and technological revolution) should be explained to the general public, especially to owners, officials, entrepreneurs and scientists and technicians through the media. will be. The transition to an innovative economy is a vital measure for the preservation of the country's integrity, the basis of interethnic harmony and territorial integrity of Uzbekistan.

Uzbekistan must use the global economic crisis as a great opportunity to radically change its economy and create an innovative economy. Creating conditions for high-tech firms and companies in different developed countries to come to Uzbekistan (or establish branches in our country) and locate their production facilities in our country, which are in a difficult situation due to this crisis, will bring great scientific, economic and spiritual benefits. would have led to an increase in practical potential. Measures to reorient the economy to national values will lead to the adaptation or radical renewal of the country's political and property elites. Thanks to the implementation of innovative economic measures, we can strictly control the creative activity of the citizens of Uzbekistan and the original scientific and technical ideas. Today, many creative, educated, intelligent and well-educated citizens of our country work in different countries, but Uzbekistan does not benefit from any innovation and technology.

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